

Planar Graph Classifier

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The field of graph drawing is concerned with creating graph embeddings and visualizing graphs in a way that is pleasing to the user and allows for a quick and accurate interpretation of the information represented by a graph. Edge crossings in the layout are proven to have negative effects and there are many approaches developed specifically for creating graph layouts without crossings. By definition, planar graphs have no edge crossings and therefore the attribute of planarity is of major importance when evaluating the quality of a graph embedding.

Figure 1: Planar Graph Layout

Figure 2: Non-Planar Graph Layout

The aim of this project is to train a classifier on images of graphs in order to determine whether they are planar. For this purpose, datasets with graphs of varying node and edge amounts from popular graph databases are fed to the networkx layout algorithms for planar and spring graph layouts. The graph embeddings are visualized with randomized node and edge sizes by matplotlib. These images are the input for a keras model based on a standard convolutional neural network structure. Training was supported with a cuda capable GPU and early stopping based on validation set accuracy was implemented. Finally the model was evaluated on a test set and loss as well as accuracy is kept as the result.

Setup:

Figure 3: Workflow of the Planar Graph Classifier project

This project is publicly available at Bitbucket (<https://bitbucket.org/Remvipomed/planargraphclassifier/>).

The README on this repository links to the datasets used and describes the steps taken during the training and evaluation. The libraries recommended are intended for GPU usage. The process was run on a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 with cuda support. It may be necessary to use different libraries and drivers if CPU or a different graphics card is used.

Preprocessing:

The first step is to load all the graph data from the different datasets and convert them into images. Positional data is gained by performing the layout algorithms of the networkx library and images are created by saving the matplotlib visualization of the plotted graphs. If networkx is able to draw the graph with a planar layout, an entry with class 1 is stored for that graph, otherwise the graph is drawn with a spring layout and is associated with class 0. The target class for each graph is stored as csv file per dataset.

Model:

Figure 2: Keras model visualization of the convolutional neural network generated by the visualkeras library

The keras model is built with the tensorflow library and is structured after a common convolutional neural network architecture of two convolutional layers followed by a MaxPooling layer. For the input of 80x80 grayscale images, 3 convolutional structures were chosen to be sufficient. Finally the

image data is flattened and fed into several dense neural network layers of decreasing size for classification. Some Dropout layers in between are integrated to battle overfitting.

Training:

Figure 3: Plotting of loss and accuracy during training of both training and validation set generated by `plot_keras_history` library

Before start of the training, the input data is split into training, validation, and test set. During the keras model training process, images are referenced from the class data and loaded in batches. Loss is calculated with binary crossentropy and an Adam optimizer is used for the learning rate. One training epoch takes about 30s to complete with GPU support. The peak accuracy of 99% is often reached within the first epoch. Sometimes the model deteriorate during training as the learning rate of the adaptive optimizer becomes too large and needs to settle in subsequent epochs.

Problems:

The most obvious issue with the methodology of this experiment is the exclusive use of networkx and matplotlib for graph layouts. This is certain to be the cause for overfitting on both the layout structure of the networkx embedding as well as the visual style of matplotlib, even though some augmentation based on randomization of node and edge size was attempted.

The imbalance in the amount of planar and non-planar graphs poses another problem. This is mitigated by using class weights during training.

Furthermore, the initial success of the training is largely dependent on the randomized initial learning rate of the adam optimizer. A bad value can set the model back to single class output.

Result:

The classifier quickly reaches an accuracy of over 99%, which can be considered an acceptable percentage for a binary classification problem. Therefore the problem of planarity detection is solvable by a neural network. As mentioned before, the images generated from the dataset were not general enough to determine the model's effectiveness on more diverse graph visualizations. However it constitutes a proof of concept and can serve as a baseline for further efforts in planarity classification.